

Course Redesign: Implementing Active Learning to Enhance Student Success

Hwangji Lu¹, Robert Smiles²

^{1,2}University of Arizona Global Campus, Chandler, AZ, USA

ABSTRACT: Delivering online courses is not a new paradigm in U.S. higher education. Online courses and programs play a significant role in providing opportunities for adult learners to further their education without sacrificing their work and family commitments. Because of the advancement of communication technologies, the educational landscape is undergoing a rapid transformation. Higher educational institutions must have a continuous improvement mindset to integrate emerging educational technologies and best instructional pedagogies into the curricula. Revising the course content and evaluating the updated course's effectiveness is imperative. This paper presents a study in which a revised course in the master's program of healthcare administration is incorporated with active learning approaches. For triangulation, a mixed-method research design is employed to collect qualitative and quantitative data from multiple sources. The results from this study confirm findings derived from prior empirical research studies. The limitations and future research are also discussed. The implications for online education instructors, instructional designers, and administrators are also presented.

KEYWORDS: Active learning, course redesign, drop-out rate, online learning, student satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

As technology rapidly develops, online teaching and learning modalities have become an indispensable part of higher education for many reasons, for example, convenience, flexibility, and lower costs (Rajeh et al., 2021). However, online learning presents unique challenges for both students and instructors. Interaction in online classrooms is quite challenging compared to traditional face-to-face in-class courses (Gopal et al., 2023; Martin & Bolliger, 2022). Education literature documents that students may experience isolation without authentic student-to-student and student-to-instructor interactions (Benková et al., 2022; Martin & Bolliger, 2022; Rajeh et al., 2021). Research has shown that in online learning, students tend to feel emotional loneliness and decide to drop out of the class or program (Gopal et al., 2023; Rajeh et al., 2021). Factors such as course content, course design, and instructional style were reported as determinants of student interaction in online classrooms (Benková et al., 2022; Bickle et al., 2019; Martin & Bolliger, 2022).

This paper is structured as follows. The second section provides a literature survey regarding course design/redesign, active learning pedagogies, instructor's roles, student satisfaction, and research questions. The third section presents research methodology, including study context, data collection, and analysis. The fourth section discusses the results of empirical analyses. Study limitations and proposed future research are disclosed in the fifth section. Lastly, the paper concludes with a summary and implications.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Course Design and Redesign

Course design and redesign are crucial in online courses and programs as they directly impact student engagement, student satisfaction, learning outcomes, and overall course success (Benková et al., 2022). Course redesign in online classrooms is not just an act of updating content. It should include a strategic initiative, including multiple pedagogies and learning strategies to improve the learning experience (Muscatello, 2023). A substantial body of literature has investigated the impacts of course redesign in recent years. Many researchers and scholars studied if and how innovations in curriculum, instructional design, instructional delivery, or pedagogy can promote student learning (Krsmanovic, 2021). Course design or redesign needs to ensure a well-structured, accessible, and interactive learning experience because students are not physically in a classroom (Benková et al., 2022). Learners desire more than static lectures and text-heavy modules. Thus, designing or redesigning online courses should involve embracing a learner-

centered approach, incorporating multimedia elements, and adopting emerging technologies (Benková et al., 2022; Muscatello, 2023). Developing online learning courses suitable for students will elevate students' enthusiasm for active learning and bring better learning outcomes (Hwang et al., 2019; Yu et al., 2022). Once the course is designed or redesigned effectively, learners will have a higher acceptance of the e-learning, increase their knowledge and skills, and improve academic performance (Gopal et al., 2021).

B. Active Learning Pedagogies

Active learning is an activity-based learning approach that allows learners to undergo a meaningful learning experience (McKinney et al., 2023). Active learning methodologies have transitioned from passive instructor-centered to student-centered learning (Rossi et al., 2021). In active learning, instructor-centered pedagogy is shifting toward a new learning paradigm where students build their understanding of a subject through learning activities (Theobald et al., 2020). The activities can vary, for instance, hands-on activities geared toward case-based, collaborative, cooperative, problem-solving, and team-based learning (Strelan et al., 2020; Theobald et al., 2020). In addition, debates in the discussion boards to engage students with their peers, peer-teach, role-playing, and simulation are also examples of active learning approaches (Collins & McLain, 2021; Pan & Fan, 2020). Active learning approaches benefit the learning process by using relevant real-world scenarios by which students can apply problem-based learning techniques to solve real-world cases (Grijpma et al., 2021). Active learning pedagogies enable students to understand new information and construct knowledge through higher order thinking rather than memorizing facts (Muscatello, 2023). Active learning empowers learners to participate actively in learning (student-centered) and be in charge of their learning instead of passively comprehending content by listening to the lecture and taking notes (Scott et al., 2024). Active learning also provides learners an authentic learning environment and makes it easier to digest, fathom, and master the learned knowledge and skills (Yu et al., 2022). Through active learning activities, students are involved directly in the content, resulting in deeper learning (Scott et al., 2024).

Active learning has its roots in the cognitive, constructivist, experiential, and social theories of learning (Muscatello, 2023; Vygotsky, 1978). According to the social constructivist paradigm, active learning promotes students to create their knowledge by actively integrating new information with their prior knowledge and experience to form new and enhanced understanding (Vygotsky, 1978). It is a shift to a student-centered instructional approach focusing on knowledge construction through performing actions that require higher-order thinking (Yu et al., 2022). Furthermore, active learning permits students to explore their attitudes or values and engage in metacognitive reflection on their learning process (Betti et al., 2022). Research suggests that students' active engagement in class positively influences various aspects of learning, including understanding, retention, and enjoyment (Ratan, 2022).

Many schools have implemented active learning techniques in health professions education to advance students' competencies in recent decades (Grijpma et al., 2021). Problem-based, case-based, inquiry-based, project-based, and team-based learning are common active learning pedagogies in various health professions education curricula. By facilitating active learning, instructors help students build individualized understandings that they can retrieve more readily than by listening to explanations alone since active learning requires students to become actively involved in their learning process (Betti et al., 2022; Ratan, 2022).

The benefits of active learning pedagogies are substantial, including boosting performance, diversity, and equity in the classroom (McKinney et al., 2023; Theobald et al., 2020). Practical active learning assignments enhance student engagement, foster motivation, facilitate learning of the course content, and develop skills in communication, conflict resolution, critical thinking, and leadership (Rossi, 2021; Theobald et al., 2020; Woods, 2020; McKinney, 2023). Active learning approaches have also improved student self-efficacy, a sense of social belonging, retention, progression, and satisfaction (Lomer & Palmer, 2023; Romanow et al., 2020). Evidence shows that integrating with active learning approaches can increase course effectiveness as self-advocacy, student self-efficacy, and academic achievement are notably enhanced (Muscatello, 2023; Pfeifer et al., 2023). Consequently, including active learning strategies could result in a reduced probability of course dropout rate.

C. Instructor's Roles

Instructor quality refers to a faculty who perceives the students' educational needs, has unique teaching skills, and knows how to meet the students' learning needs (Gopal et al., 2021; Shehzad & Charles, 2023). Instructor quality positively impacts students' satisfaction with online classes (Gopal et al., 2021). Undeniably, instructors play a pivotal role in promoting their students' engagement. They can prompt their students to engage, monitor the learning process, and address students' questions and concerns

(Grijpma et al., 2021). Instructors must focus more on creating an interactive and supportive online learning atmosphere to reduce students' feelings of isolation in the virtual environment (Yu et al., 2022). Zilka et al.'s (2018) study found an association between the lack of instructor presence and feelings of isolation, deterring motivation in the online learning environment. Student's feeling of isolation affects their ability to learn, engage, and interact with their peers and instructors. Zilka et al.'s study suggested that the imperative role of the instructor is to engage students in meaningful learning experiences. In Shehzad and Charles's study (2023), mixed-methods research was designed to investigate instructor's social presence and its impact on student engagement. Their findings confirmed that the instructor's social presence is key to student engagement and attrition. Furthermore, Ratan et al. (2022) conducted an exploratory survey with 322 undergraduate students. Their study concluded that students' perceived learning, competence, and class enjoyment are significantly related to instructor social presence, which is augmented through active learning strategies. Therefore, it is an impetus to highlight the important role of instructors' social presence in online education. Moreover, the instructor's prompt feedback enhances student learning experience and satisfaction (Gopal et al., 2021). It has been found that timely feedback helps develop a strong relationship between instructors and students, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes. Providing timely assessment feedback can help students in online classes improve their understanding of the course materials, participation, and interaction (Martin et al., 2018). Good feedback practice benefits student learning and improves students' learning experience.

Within an online asynchronous learning platform, a faculty facilitator's role is to engage with students and promote an active learning environment. Instructors should provide motivation through clear expectations using a variety of modalities such as email and classroom announcements. Wuttikietpaiboon's (2012) phenomenological study suggested that the quality of student responses and engagement within online discussion forums are influenced by the role of the instructor as a motivator to promote a positive learning experience. As an example, instructors need to maintain a student-focused approach and provide critical analysis within a positive environment of thoughtful praise and applicable feedback. Wuttikietpaiboon further explained that four interrelated domains are essential to an online instructor's role. First, an intellectual role centered on achieving the aspects set forth regarding defined weekly learning objectives and course objectives. Secondly, an online instructor's role involves social presence, and instructors are tasked with modeling positive online communication processes through active participation during weekly discussions and feedback processes. Third, it is vitally important that online instructors provide a managerial presence. This domain centers on leadership, focusing on due dates and classroom milestones; additionally, it is critically important for online instructors to monitor discussion rooms and motivate students who respond less. Lastly, the role of an online instructor is to provide technical guidance and proficiency while navigating the online classroom. Modeling technical and scholarly proficiency aids students in becoming comfortable within the online learning platform. Russel's (2013) study found that the role of online instructors includes self-reflection and the ability to become a true participant within the online classroom. The process involves active engagement through meaningful Socratic questioning and content-applicable discussion responses. This process ensures that students will experience and participate in an environment of shared ideas and trust and develop habits associated with lifetime learning.

D. Student Satisfaction

The imperative parameter for measuring the success of online education is student satisfaction (Li & Asante, 2021; Mutawa & Sruthi, 2024) because it can impact students' engagement, motivation, learning, performance, success, and ultimately retention and graduation rates (Martin & Bolliger, 2022). Students' satisfaction with their learning experience shapes the success of online education (Azizan et al., 2022). Student satisfaction, a complex construct, is found to be intertwined with many other factors. Literature has documented that factors that have the potential to influence student satisfaction in online learning environments are active learning, course design, quality of the instructor, interaction with the instructor, and instructor's timely feedback (Gopal et al., 2023; Martin & revealed that students value their instructor's feedback and guidance to improve the quality of their work, which keeps the students on track and impacts student satisfaction, academic performance, and learning outcomes. As students engage in an instructional activity involving interaction with an instructor, they become focused on the content. Because they are actively engaged, students will likely recall Bolliger, 2022). Bickle et al. (2019) reported that students' perceptions of the course quality relied heavily on their interface with their instructors and the ability to express their opinions during online learning (Bickle et al., 2019). A study by Gain et al. (2021) the knowledge and lessons learned. By learning the content in such a state of awareness, students tend to report that they learned well (Ratan, 2022).

E. Research Questions

The quality of course content is vital because it impacts how students learn, retain information, and achieve the anticipated learning outcomes. The main objective of this study was to appraise the effectiveness of a course redesign incorporated active learning approaches. We aimed to investigate the following questions:

- (1) What are the students' perceptions and experiences regarding various learning assessments in the revised course?
- (2) Do students learn differently in the revised course?
- (3) Are there any different satisfaction levels between students taking the old version and the redesigned course?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Study Context

We employed a mixed-method research design for this study to investigate the students' perceptions of a redesigned course to understand if the course content met its purpose of revision and students' needs. The study population included learners enrolled in the master's program in healthcare administration at a university in the United States's southwestern region. The university's global campus has offered the master's program in healthcare administration exclusively online since 2009. The master's program in healthcare administration traditionally incorporated two discussion boards and one written paper weekly in the 6-week courses. On the other hand, the revised only has one discussion board per week, and many of the discussion boards and assignments in this revised course are case scenario based. We also include multimedia presentations for Post Your Introduction and the week 2 assignment to enhance students' oral communication skills. In week 4, we include a Peer Review Discussion Board to promote student-to-student interactions.

Three hundred forty-three students enrolled in this redesigned course from July 2023 to June 2024. The Institutional Review Board at the university approved this research proposal. We designed an in-house student survey sent out to those students who had enrolled in the studied course from July 2023 to June 2024. An email communication informed students about the purpose of the study. The email clearly stated that participation in this project was voluntary, and no penalty would apply for early withdrawal.

B. Data Collection

We designed an in-house student survey that purposely asked students about their perception and experiences with various learning assessments in this redesigned course. The ratings were on a five-point Likert-type scale from strongly disagree = 1, disagree = 2, neutral = 3, agree = 4, to strongly agree = 5. We also included the university's standardized end-of-course survey to ascertain students' level of satisfaction with the course from students enrolling in the old version and students enrolling in the revised one. The ratings were on a five-point Likert-type scale from strongly disagree = 0, disagree = 1, neutral = 2, agree = 3, to strongly agree = 4.

We obtained students' verbal comments captured by two surveys and the journal entries in which students wrote their reflections on their learning in this redesigned course. Content analysis was used to examine students' narratives. The collected qualitative data from multiple sources enable us to triangulate the research findings and provide more insights that allow us to explain the phenomenon better, which increases the credibility of this research.

C. Data Analysis

Once quantitative data were collected and verified confidently, the SPSS Statistical software suite was used to manipulate the data and conduct statistical analysis. Before analyzing survey data, descriptive statistical procedures were used to profile the characteristics of the sample as a whole. The measures of central tendency and variability were obtained. The data were analyzed by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine whether students in two different versions of courses exhibited differences in academic achievements and satisfaction. We utilized the thematic analysis method to identify patterns and themes in the collected qualitative data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. The Findings from The In-House Survey

We sent out 343 in-house student surveys, but only 48 students responded to the survey, which resulted in a 14% response rate. The first research question was formulated to understand the students' perceptions of various learning assessments in this redesigned

course. Table 1 presents the in-house survey results expressed by the percentage of students who either agreed or strongly agreed with the survey item.

TABLE 1. STUDENT SURVEY RESULTS EXPRESSED IN PERCENTAGE

Survey Item	N	% of Agree + Strongly Agree
Discussion Boards and Assignments prepared me to deal with various aspects of health care information systems and management.	48	77.09
Week 2 Assignment (IT Governance) helped me polish my PP Presentation and oral presentation skills.	48	77.09
The Final Paper Prep helped me get started on my research and development of the final paper.	48	79.18
Peer review helped me develop my final paper and practice the skill of providing feedback to others.	48	70.84
The HIPAA training helped me expand my knowledge in HIPAA.	48	68.75
This course increased my knowledge of the health care industry.	48	87.50

The survey item, ‘This course increased my knowledge in healthcare,’ received the highest score. About 87.5% of surveyed students either agreed or strongly agreed with this statement. Here are some verbal comments from students. *“I honestly found all of the weeks assignments to be very enlightening.” “The text, discussions, and assignments provided opportunities to learn more about the healthcare industry in an engaging manner.” “I feel much more confident of my HCIS knowledge.” “I can apply what I learned in my career and add to the conversations had within our company and industry current events.”*

The ‘final paper prep’ survey item received the second-highest score at 79.18%. Students appreciated the opportunity to work ahead for their final paper. In terms of Peer Review for the Final Paper Prep, it depends on student’s assigned peer. One student commented, *“I did not like the peer of mine, nor did I find it helpful in anyway.”* Other students had pleasant experience in this learning activity and voiced positive, *“The prep and the peer assessment provided key insights on what would be key points required for the final paper.” “It was nice to have multiple students provide feedback.” “My classmates have great feedback.” “I took the feedback to present a great final paper.” “The peer reviews were helpful in providing transparent feedback on areas of the paper requiring improvement.” “Having the review if my peers were helpful. It gave me time to review and make adjustments to my work.”*

Two survey items, ‘Discussion Boards and Assignments prepared me to deal with various aspects of health care information systems and management’ and ‘Week 2 Assignment (IT Governance) helped me polish my PP Presentation and oral presentation skills’ had the same score at 77.09%. We have incorporated several case-based case scenarios into discussion boards and assignments. Students had positive experience in discussion boards. Below are some comments. *“Concepts in each discussion fit my career path as it addresses topics I’ve seen throughout my career experience.” “Discussion boards were very engaging which promotes learning.” “The discussion boards covered an array of topics and engaged in thoughtful assessment of information presented in the text and other resources.” “I feel as if I have a better idea of how healthcare information technology plays in the role of patient care and hospital administration, I have learned a lot of very valuable information.”*

For the video presentation, some students disliked the assignment because they spent lots of time creating a video or they were afraid of public speaking. However, other students accepted the challenge, got out of their comfort zone, and saw it as an opportunity to grow and learn. One student said, *“Allowed me to practice public speaking and time management.”* Another student commented, *“It was fun, challenging, and engaging.”* One student really saw the value of this exercise and said, *“This was excellent practice in both PowerPoint in a business setting as well as giving an oral presentation.”*

On the other hand, nearly 69% of surveyed students felt that the HIPAA training helped them expand their knowledge of HIPAA. We are not surprised by this result because most of our students have worked for healthcare organizations. They have taken annual HIPAA training at their jobs, so some students felt it was repetitive. Instead, positive comments include, *“I already do HIPAA*

training for work but this is always helpful.” “I understood a good deal about HIPAA from previous employment, but I did learn a few things that I didn't know previously.” “My knowledge in HIPAA is stronger.”

B. The Findings From Key Course Metrics

The second research question investigated if students learn differently in the revised course. As Table 2 shown, the revised course had a lower GPA and a higher fail rate when compared with the old version, even though they were not statistically significant. However, we are glad that the revised course had a 4% lower drop and 2% higher progression rates.

TABLE 2. KEY METRICS

Data Source	Old Version (N = 337)		Revised Version (N=343) Changes
	GPA	3.64	
Fail	2%	4%	2%
Drop	9%	5%	-4%
Progression	82%	84%	2%

C. The Findings from The End of Course Survey

The third research question explored the levels of student satisfaction in the revised course. Since we have had a pool of faculty teaching this course, we only included the classes from five faculty who had taught both years to examine the end-of-course survey (EOCS) data. The assessment of the university administered the standardized EOCS to some selected students. The EOCS data shows that 65 out of 211 surveys were returned in the revised course, resulting in a 30.8% response rate, while 42 out of 153 surveys were returned in the revised course, resulting in a 27.5% response rate.

We were surprised to see lower overall scores in the revised course, as displayed in Table 3. Among all survey items, “The quality of education meeting my expectations” and “Clear instructions for completing assignments” were two with higher scores in the revised course. However, students in the revised course gave lower scores for all survey items related to their instructors. It is interesting because five faculty are experienced instructors in our program. They have taught this course for several years. The more they teach, the better they will be. When we reviewed students’ verbal comments, we found no complaints supporting this rating. Instructor’s timely and useful feedback helps students succeed in the online classrooms. In Gan *et al.*’s (2021) and Gopal *et al.*’s (2021) studies, the research findings confirmed that instructors need to provide timely and constructive feedback to help students learn more effectively. Accordingly, students will report higher satisfaction and exhibit better learning outcomes and academic performances.

TABLE 3. EOCS SURVEY RESULTS IN TWO YEARS

Question	Old Version (N=42)	Revised Version (N=65)
Comprehensive Items		
Recommending this course.	3.24	3.22
The quality of education meeting my expectations.	3.19	3.26
Course Assessment		
Clear instruction given for grading.	3.45	3.31
Assignments requiring critical thinking.	3.50	3.45
Hard work required to earn a good grade.	3.62	3.54
Clear instructions for completing assignments.	3.05	3.09
Engaging course content	3.36	3.35

Instructor Assessment

Recommending this instructor.	3.38	3.22
The instructor adding his/her expertise.	3.52	3.40
The instructor communicating high expectation.	3.52	3.51
The instructor fostering critical thinking.	3.57	3.42
The instructor promoting active participation.	3.57	3.43
The instructor offering consistent grading.	3.43	3.28
The instructor giving timely feedback.	3.29	3.23
The instructor giving useful feedback.	3.33	3.28
The instructor's feedback aligning with her/his stated expectations.	3.45	3.38
	3.40	3.30

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Three limitations were identified in this study. First, this research focused on one course in the master's program in healthcare administration. Therefore, the findings drawn from this research are not generalizable to any graduate courses at other programs of the university or other universities. The second limitation was a low % response rate of 14% from the in-house student survey. A low response rate poses a non-response bias, which could skew the overall results. To compare the EOCS results fairly, we only included those courses taught by the same instructors in both years. Indeed, we have more than 10 qualified instructors to teach this course in both years.

The third limitation concerns confounding factors, such as students' job status, perceptions, or background, which may interfere with students' learning and objective course evaluation. For example, according to our colleagues' findings from unpublished studies, when students did not earn a good grade, they tended to rate lower scores in the end-of-course survey. As shown in Table 2, the GPA and fail rate in the revised course were slightly lower than the old version's. It is possible that students in the revised course marked lower scores for their instructors who have taught this course for many years. Additionally, in the revised course, we had some students from the School of Business, while we did not have students from the School of Business in the old version. Therefore, another research study with the same research design should be conducted in the near future to validate the findings from this study.

CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this research was to evaluate the effectiveness of a revised course in the master's program of healthcare administration. Understanding students' experience and satisfaction is fundamental to improving the course curriculum and enriching the student's learning experience. The in-house survey revealed that 87.5% of students agreed or strongly agreed, 'This course increased my knowledge in healthcare.' Students enjoyed a variety of assessments offered in this course. This revised version shows a lower GPA, EOCS, a higher fail rate, a better progression rate, and a lower drop rate. Our findings align with the literature (Lomer & Palmer, 2023; Romanow et al., 2020) that active learning approaches can increase course effectiveness and reduce the probability of course dropout rates.

The university's standardized end-of-course survey is a continued effort to gather students' feedback systematically. The scores for survey items related to instructors are slightly lower than those in the old version. Numerous research studies (Gain et al., 2021; Gopal et al., 2021; Grijpma et al., 2021; Shehzad & Charles, 2023; Ratan et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2022) have shown that instructors are crucial to students' online learning experience and satisfaction. Thus, providing the tools needed to perform the required tasks and developing the instructor's effective pedagogical strategies to create caring and engaging online learning environments are critically important. Furthermore, it is necessary to continue to provide coaching programs to instructors who underperform according to the university's standards

This study has three important implications for instructional designers, instructors, and administrators. First, courses must be revised and updated regularly to keep content relevant and effective for adult learners. Incorporating active learning pedagogies could promote active participation, generate meaningful discussions, and cultivate critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Second, to

ensure that students learn from the most up-to-date content, instructors should add or update the latest information while facilitating the classes and providing individualized and timely feedback. Third, there is a need to offer professional development opportunities and instill a performance evaluation system for instructors to ensure that instructors provide quality instruction and education to learners.

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